

Key indicators of mapping inequalities in educational achievements in Europe

Working Paper 1

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Author: Isa Steinmann, Zsófia Tomka, Aggeliki Yfanti, Dániel Bremer

Contributors: Lihong Huang, Maria Symeonaki, István György

Design, Typeset and Layout: María Arguedas, Joan Ventura, Veronica Arduino

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1. Introduction

This documentation presents the methodology of mapping longitudinal trends of inequalities in educational achievement in Europe through re-analysis of existing data from large-scale international educational assessment studies. The aim of this working paper is to give background information about the indicators of inequalities and the underlying data forming the trends that will be visualised on the STRIDE-map: <https://stride-research.eu/interactive-map/>

2. Data and methods used to create the underlying data on key inequality indicators

We use already collected, representative data for the primary and lower secondary school level from 27 Member States of the European Union, Norway and UK. We need data that provides both test and background questionnaire data to compute indicators for inequalities in test outcomes between social groups indicated by gender, socioeconomic status (SES), immigration status, and school location as urban or rural. Specific data re-analysed include all the European countries that participated in: 1) Progress In International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) all cycles from 2001-2021 on Grade 4 in primary schools; 2) Trends In International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) all cycles from 2003-2023 on Grade 4 in primary schools and Grade 8 in lower secondary schools; 3) the International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS) 2009, 2016 and 2022 on Grade 8 in lower secondary schools; 4) the OECD Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) all cycles from 2000 – 2022 on Grade 9 in lower secondary schools.

Our analyses have excluded data from TIMSS advanced studies due to the fact that out of the 29 countries of interest, only five participated in TA2008 and only six participated in TA2015.

2.1. Country and time coverage of the data analysed

All 29 countries of interest of STRIDE project have participated in all/most study cycles of PISA. Table 2.1 presents country and time coverage of data available from IEA studies: PIRLS, TIMSS or ICCS.

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	TIMSS Grade 4						PIRLS Grade 4					TIMSS Grade 8						ICCS Grade 8		
	2003	2007	2011	2015	2019	2023	2001	2006	2011	2016	2021	2003	2007	2011	2015	2019	2023	2009	2016	2022
Austria		x	x		x			x	x	x	x			x			x	x		
Belgium	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x						x	x	
Bulgaria				x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x					x	x	x
Croatia			x	x	x				x		x			x					x	x
Cyprus	x			x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x		x
Czech Republic		x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x			x	x		
Denmark		x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x							x	x	x
Estonia												x						x	x	x
Finland			x	x	x	x			x	x	x			x		x	x	x	x	
France				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x					x	x			x
Germany		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x					x	x
Greece							x											x		
Hungary	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			
Ireland			x	x	x	x			x	x	x			x	x	x	x	x		
Italy	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Latvia	x	x			x	x	x	x		x	x	x						x	x	x
Lithuania	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Luxembourg								x										x		
Malta			x		x				x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x	x
Netherlands	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x						x	x	x
Norway	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Poland			x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x			x				x		x
Portugal			x	x	x	x			x	x	x			x		x	x			
Romania			x			x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x	x			x
Slovak Republic		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x				x		x
Slovenia	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x
Spain			x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x				x		x
Sweden		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
UK /England	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x		
UK / Northern Ireland			x	x	x				x	x	x			x						
UK / Scotland	x	x					x	x				x	x							
Total EU participants	11	15	23	23	25	23	18	21	25	24	25	17	14	19	9	12	15	23	15	19

Note: x indicating more than one group samples.

2.2. Methods used to compute inequality indicators

When computing the educational inequality indicators, the base consisted of test outcomes in different domains (but all based on standardised tests of school achievement). These domains were the following:

- reading (based on PISA and PIRLS);
- mathematics (PISA, TIMSS);
- science (PISA, TIMSS);
- civic and citizenship knowledge (ICCS).
- gender (a = girls, b = boys);
- socioeconomic status (SES) (a = at least one parent/guardian with a higher education degree, b = no parent/guardian with a higher education degree);
- immigration status (a = students not born in country, b = students born in country);
- school location (a = rural (up to 15,000 live in area), b = not rural (more than 15,000 live in area)).

Questions which the breakdowns were based on were not available for every study, every year and every country, see Section 3 below for more detailed information on this and the variables used, by survey. Based on the test outcomes and the groups we defined, we calculated 10 inequality indicators to include in the spreadsheets:

- mean test scores and breakdowns by the social groups described above (indicator “i1”);
- mean test score achieved by social group breakdown category in percent of total population mean in country (indicator “i2”);
- percent of absolute low performers in test scores (e.g., achievement level 1 in PIRLS) (indicator “i3”);
- ratios of test score means by social group breakdown categories (indicators “i5”, “i6”, “i7”, and “i8”);
- relative test score by intersectional breakdowns by social group (as compared to the total population mean in country) (indicators “i9”, “i10”, “i11”).

We originally calculated an additional indicator (“i4”), the percent of relative low performers in test scores (achieving less than 60% of country mean test score), but decided to exclude it from the spreadsheets altogether due to a very low number of observations in too many cases.

When constructing the indicators, we accounted for the complex sampling designs of the studies by including complex weights. In order to arrive at a national mean test score, we first computed means at the student level from the 5 plausible values provided for each test score in the dataset (this procedure was based on Rubin’s (1987) rules). For this, for the merging of the country datafiles, as well as for the estimation of the country and breakdown means, we used the software IEA IDB Analyzer. This also made it possible to compute standard errors and confidence intervals in the case of indicator 1.

3. Included data and indicators codebooks

The naming convention of the indicator variables reflects the different characteristics of the underlying data and indicators (see Figure 3 for an example).

Figure 3 Exemplary illustration of indicator naming convention

The following sections give detailed information about the included data per source study.

3.1. Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS)

Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS; Mullis et al., 2023) is an international large-scale assessment on reading acquisition contexts and reading achievement outcomes of children at the end of primary school. PIRLS contains both standardised student tests on reading achievement as well as comprehensive context questionnaires, both for the students, their parents or legal guardians (home questionnaire), their teachers, their school principals, as well as a questionnaire on the school systems’ reading curricula.

The PIRLS definition of reading achievement is: “Reading literacy is the ability to understand and use those written language forms required by society and/or valued by the individual. Readers can construct meaning from texts in a variety of forms. They read to learn, to participate in communities of readers in school and everyday life, and for enjoyment” (Mullis & Martin, 2019, p. 6).

PIRLS collects data from representative samples of students in grade 4 (even though some countries deviate from this target grade) by first drawing stratified samples of schools and then intact classes from these schools (see von Davier et al. (2023) for more information). PIRLS has been conducted every five years since 2001 (the 2021 assessment deviated from earlier cycles due to pandemic-related disruptions).

Table 3.1.1 contains an overview of the source instruments and original variable names of the constructs of interest across PIRLS cycles. Note that the construct ‘immigration status’ was reported in student questionnaires in earlier cycles and in home questionnaires in later cycles. Both ‘immigration status’ and ‘school location’ were not included in all PIRLS cycles. Table 3.1.2 describes the spreadsheet indicators that were derived from PIRLS data, as well as details on their availability across PIRLS cycles.

Table 3.1.1 Source instruments and variable names in ICCS

Construct	Source instruments	Variable names in source data				
		2001	2006	2011	2016	2021
Reading achievement	Student tests	asrrea01– asrrea05	asrrea01– asrrea05	asrrea01– asrrea05	asrrea01– asrrea05	asrrea01– asrrea05
Gender	Student questionnaire	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex
Socioeconomic status	Home questionnaire	asbhedef, asbhedum	asbhledf, asbhledm	asbh17a, asbh17b	asbh18a, asbh18b	asbh15a, asbh15b
Immigration status	Student quest. in 2001 & 2006; home quest. in 2016 & 2021	asbgbrn1	asbgbrn1	-	asbh03a	asbh02a
School location	School questionnaire	-	acbgctas	acbg05a	acbg05a	acbg05a

Table 3.1.2 Source instruments and variable names in ICCS

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pg4r_i1	Mean reading test score	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_2a	Mean reading test score by gender: girls	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_2b	Mean reading test score by gender: boys	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_3a	Mean reading test score by SES: at least one parent/guardian with a higher education degree	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_3b	Mean reading test score by SES: no parent/guardian with a higher education degree	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_4a	Mean reading test score by immigration status: students not born in country	2001, 2006, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_4b	Mean reading test score by immigration status: students born in country	2001, 2006, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_5a	Mean reading test score by school location: rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i1_5b	Mean reading test score by school location: not rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i2_2a	Mean reading test score achieved by girls in % of total population mean in country	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i2_2b	Mean reading test score achieved by boys in % of total population mean in country	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i2_3a	Mean reading test score achieved by students with at least one parent/guardian with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pg4r_i2_3b	Mean reading test score achieved by students with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i2_4a	Mean reading test score achieved by students not born in country in % of total population mean in country	2001, 2006, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i2_4b	Mean reading test score achieved by students born in country in % of total population mean in country	2001, 2006, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i2_5a	Mean reading test score achieved by students in rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i2_5b	Mean reading test score achieved by students in not rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i3	Percent of absolute low performers in reading	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i5	Ratio of reading test score means: students with at least one parent/guardian with a higher education degree vs. students with no parent/guardian with a higher education degree)	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i6	Ratio reading test score means: boys vs. girls	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i7	Ratio of reading test score means: student born in country vs. student not born in country	2001, 2006, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i8	Ratio of reading test score means: not rural vs. rural school location	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i9_aa	Mean reading test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent/guardian with a higher education degree & girls	2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i10_ab	Mean reading test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent/guardian with a higher education degree & not rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i10_ba	Mean reading test scores by SES & school location: no parent/guardian with a higher education degree & rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i10_bb	Mean reading test scores by SES & school location: no parent/guardian with a higher education degree & not rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pg4r_i11_aa	Mean reading test scores by gender & school location: girls & rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i11_ab	Mean reading test scores by gender & school location: girls & not rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021
pg4r_i11_ba	Mean reading test scores by gender & school location: boys & rural	2006, 2011, 2016, 2021

3.2. Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS)

The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) is an international large-scale student assessment study focusing on measuring student achievement in the domains of mathematics and science in two age groups: in grade 4 and in grade 8. It is conducted every four years since 1995, thus making it possible to monitor changes in student achievement over time. In the spreadsheet, in accordance with the time frame of the database, indicators for the years 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023 were included.

Apart from the student test questionnaires which measure achievement, the survey also comprises a number of context questionnaires which gather information on factors influencing student achievement. These take the form of school, teacher, student and home questionnaires (the latter only implemented in the grade 4 age group from the year 2011 onwards). TIMSS also gathers data on national curricula and their implementation (see Mullis et al 2017 and Mullis et al 2021 as examples).

Tables 3.2.1 to 3.2.4 contain detailed information on source instruments and variable names for both domains and both age groups, as well as a condensed version of the indicator codebooks of the spreadsheet indicators. Here, it has to be noted that it was not possible to construct the socioeconomic status variable for the years 2003 and 2007, and the immigration status variable for the year 2011 in the case of grade 4. For grade 8, no such issue exists. Furthermore, in both age groups, in the case of Belgium, only indicators for the Flemish region are included in the spreadsheet.

Table 3.2.1 Source instruments and variable names in TIMSS Grade 4

Construct	Source instruments	Variable names in source data					
		2003	2007	2011	2015	2019	2023
Mathematics achievement	Student tests	asmmat01 – asmmat05	asmmat01– asmmat05	asmmat01 – asmmat05	asmmat01– asmmat05	asmmat01– asmmat05	asmmat01– asmmat05
Science achievement	Student tests	asssci01– asssci05	asssci01– asssci05	asssci01– asssci05	asssci01– asssci05	asssci01– asssci05	asssci01– asssci05
Gender	Student questionnaire	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex
Socio-economic status	Home questionnaire	-	-	asdhedup	asdhedup	asdhedup	asdhedup
Immigration status	Student questionnaire	asbgborn	as4gborn	-	asbg07	asbg07	asbg07

Table 3.2.2 Indicator codebook for TIMSS Grade 4-based spreadsheet indicators

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg4m_i1	Mean mathematics test score	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i1_2a	Mean mathematics test score by gender: girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i1_2b	Mean mathematics test score by gender: boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg4m_i1_3a	Mean mathematics test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i1_3b	Mean mathematics test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i1_4a	Mean mathematics test score by migrant status: migrant	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i1_4b	Mean mathematics test score by migrant status: not migrant	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i1_5a	Mean mathematics test score by location: rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i1_5b	Mean mathematics test score by location: not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i2_2a	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by girls in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i2_2b	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by boys in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i2_3a	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students with at least one parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i2_3b	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students with no parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i2_4a	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students not born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i2_4b	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg4m_i2_5a	Mean mathematics test score achieved by students in rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i2_5b	Mean mathematics test score achieved by students in not rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i3	Percent of absolute low performers in mathematics	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i5	Ratio of mathematics test score means: students with at least one parent with a higher education degree vs. students with no parent with a higher education degree	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i6	Ratio of mathematics test score means: boys vs. girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i7	Ratio of mathematics test score means: students not born in country vs. students born in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i8	Ratio of mathematics test score means: not rural vs. rural school location	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i9_a	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & boys	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i9_b	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & girls	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i9_c	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: no parent with higher education degree & boys	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i9_d	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: no parent with a higher education degree & girls	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i10_a	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg4m_i10_b	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i10_c	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i10_d	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i11_a	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: girls & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i11_b	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: girls & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i11_c	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: boys & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4m_i11_d	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: boys & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1	Mean science test score	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1_2a	Mean science test score by gender: girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1_2b	Mean science test score by gender: boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1_3a	Mean science test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1_3b	Mean science test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1_4a	Mean science test score by migrant status: migrant	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg4sc_i1_4b	Mean science test score by migrant status: not migrant	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1_5a	Mean science test score by location: rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i1_5b	Mean science test score by location: not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_2a	Mean science testscore achieved by girls in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_2b	Mean science testscore achieved by boys in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_3a	Mean science testscore achieved by students with at least one parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_3b	Mean science testscore achieved by students with no parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_4a	Mean science testscore achieved by students not born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_4b	Mean science testscore achieved by students born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_5a	Mean science testscore achieved by students in rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i2_5b	Mean science testscore achieved by students in not rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i3	Percent of absolute low performers in science	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg4sc_i5	Ratio of science test score means: students with at least one parent with a higher education degree vs. students with no parent with a higher education degree	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i6	Ratio of science test score means: boys vs. girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i7	Ratio of science test score means: students not born in country vs. students born in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i8	Ratio of science test score means: not rural vs. rural school location	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i9_a	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & boys	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i9_b	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & girls	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i9_c	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: no parent with higher education degree & boys	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i9_d	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: no parent with a higher education degree & girls	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i10_a	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i10_b	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i10_c	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i10_d	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i11_a	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: girls & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i11_b	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: girls & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg4sc_i11_c	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: boys & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg4sc_i11_d	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: boys & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Table 3.2.3 Source instruments and variable names in TIMSS Grade 8

Construct	Source instruments	Variable names in source data					
		2003	2007	2011	2015	2019	2023
Mathematics achievement	Student tests	asmmat01 – asmmat05	asmmat01–asmmat05	asmmat01 – asmmat05	asmmat01–asmmat05	asmmat01–asmmat05	asmmat01–asmmat05
Science achievement	Student tests	asssci01–asssci05	asssci01–asssci05	asssci01–asssci05	asssci01–asssci05	asssci01–asssci05	asssci01–asssci05
Gender	Student questionnaire	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex	itsex
Socio-economic status	Home questionnaire	-	-	asdhedup	asdhedup	asdhedup	asdhedup
Immigration status	Student questionnaire	bsbgborn	bs4gborn	bsbg09a	bsbg10a	bsbg09a	bsbg09a
School location	School questionnaire	bcbgcomu	bc4gcomu	bcbg05a	bcbg05a	bcbg05a	bcbg05a

Table 3.2.4 Indicator codebook for TIMSS Grade 8-based spreadsheet indicators

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg8m_i1	Mean mathematics test score	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_2a	Mean mathematics test score by gender: girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_2b	Mean mathematics test score by gender: boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_3a	Mean mathematics test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_3b	Mean mathematics test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_4a	Mean mathematics test score by migrant status: migrant	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_4b	Mean mathematics test score by migrant status: not migrant	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_5a	Mean mathematics test score by location: rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i1_5b	Mean mathematics test score by location: not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i2_2a	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by girls in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i2_2b	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by boys in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg8m_i2_3a	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students with at least one parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i2_3b	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students with no parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i2_4a	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students not born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i2_4b	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i2_5a	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students in rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i2_5b	Mean mathematics testscore achieved by students in not rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i3	Percent of absolute low performers in mathematics	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i5	Ratio of mathematics test score means: students with at least one parent with a higher education degree vs. students with no parent with a higher education degree	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i6	Ratio of mathematics test score means: boys vs. girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i7	Ratio of mathematics test score means: students not born in country vs. students born in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i8	Ratio of mathematics test score means: not rural vs. rural school location	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg8m_i9_a	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i9_b	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i9_c	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: no parent with higher education degree & boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i9_d	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & gender: no parent with a higher education degree & girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i10_a	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i10_b	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i10_c	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i10_d	Relative mathematics test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i11_a	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: girls & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i11_b	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: girls & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i11_c	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: boys & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8m_i11_d	Relative mathematics test scores by gender & school location: boys & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg8sc_i1	Mean science test score	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_2a	Mean science test score by gender: girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_2b	Mean science test score by gender: boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_3a	Mean science test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_3b	Mean science test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_4a	Mean science test score by migrant status: migrant	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_4b	Mean science test score by migrant status: not migrant	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_5a	Mean science test score by location: rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i1_5b	Mean science test score by location: not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i2_2a	Mean science testscore achieved by girls in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i2_2b	Mean science testscore achieved by boys in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i2_3a	Mean science testscore achieved by students with at least one parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg8sc_i2_3b	Mean science testscore achieved by students with no parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i2_4a	Mean science testscore achieved by students not born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i2_4b	Mean science testscore achieved by students born in country in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i2_5a	Mean science testscore achieved by students in rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i2_5b	Mean science testscore achieved by students in not rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i3	Percent of absolute low performers in science	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i5	Ratio of science test score means: students with at least one parent with a higher education degree vs. students with no parent with a higher education degree	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i6	Ratio of science test score means: boys vs. girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i7	Ratio of science test score means: students not born in country vs. students born in country	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i8	Ratio of science test score means: not rural vs. rural school location	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i9_a	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i9_b	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
tg8sc_i9_c	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: no parent with higher education degree & boys	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i9_d	Relative science test scores by SES & gender: no parent with a higher education degree & girls	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i10_a	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i10_b	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i10_c	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i10_d	Relative science test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i11_a	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: girls & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i11_b	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: girls & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i11_c	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: boys & rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023
tg8sc_i11_d	Relative science test scores by gender & school location: boys & not rural	2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, 2023

3.3 International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS)

The International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS) is a large-scale international student assessment study aiming to investigate the ways in which young people are prepared to assume their civic responsibilities and undertake their roles as citizens. ICCS reports on students' knowledge and understanding of, as well as beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours towards topics related to civics and citizenship (see Schulz et al 2022).

Assessment is targeted at students enrolled in the eighth grade, provided that the average age of students at this year level is 13,5 years or above. In countries where the average age of students in Grade 8 is less than 13,5 years, Grade 9 is defined as the target population.

In addition, ICCS collects rich contextual data on the organisation and content of civic and citizenship education in the curriculum, teacher qualifications and experiences, teaching practices, school environment, and home and community support. This data is collected through student, teacher, and school questionnaires.

Tables 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 below contain detailed information on source instruments and variable names, and an indicator codebook of the spreadsheet indicators.

Table 3.3.1 Source instruments and variable names ICCS

Construct	Source instruments	Variable names in source data		
		2009	2016	2022
citizenship education	Student tests	PV1CIV-PV5CIV	PV1CIV-PV5CIV	PV1CIV-PV5CIV
Gender	Student questionnaire	SGENDER	S_GENDER	IS4G02
Socio-economic status	Student questionnaire	HISCED	S_HISCED	S_HISCED
Immigration status	Student questionnaire	IS2G04A	IS3G04A	IS4G04A
School location	School questionnaire	IC2G23	IC3G20	IC4G23

Table 3.3.2 Indicator codebook for ICCS-based spreadsheet

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
iccs_i1	Mean civics and citizenship education test score	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_2a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by gender: girls	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_2b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by gender: boys	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_3a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_3b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_4a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by migrant status: migrant	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_4b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by migrant status: not migrant	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_5a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by location: rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i1_5b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score by location: not rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i2_2a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by girls in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i2_2b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by boys in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i2_3a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by students with at least one parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i2_3b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by students with no parent with a higher education degree in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i2_4a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by students not born in country in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
iccs_i2_4b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by students born in country in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i2_5a	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by students in rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i2_5b	Mean civics and citizenship education test score achieved by students in not rural schools in % of total population mean in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i3	Percent of absolute low performers in civics and citizenship education	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i4	Percent of relative low performers in civics and citizenship education	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i5	Ratio of civics and citizenship education test score means: students with at least one parent with a higher education degree vs. students with no parent with a higher education degree	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i6	Ratio of civics and citizenship education test score means: boys vs. girls	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i7	Ratio of civics and citizenship education test score means: students not born in country vs. students born in country	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i8	Ratio of civics and citizenship education test score means: not rural vs. rural school location	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i9_a	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & boys	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i9_b	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & gender: at least one parent with a higher education degree & girls	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i9_c	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & gender: no parent with higher education degree & boys	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i9_d	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & gender: no parent with a higher education degree & girls	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i10_a	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i10_b	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & school location: at least one parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2009, 2016, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
iccs_i10_c	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i10_d	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by SES & school location: no parent with a higher education degree & not rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i11_a	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by gender & school location: girls & rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i11_b	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by gender & school location: girls & not rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i11_c	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by gender & school location: boys & rural	2009, 2016, 2022
iccs_i11_d	Relative civics and citizenship education test scores by gender & school location: boys & not rural	2009, 2016, 2022

3.4 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA)

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The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) was created by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). PISA aims to measuring the 15-year-olds' ability to use their knowledge of mathematics and science, reading, and skills to meet real-life challenges. Since 2012 PISA provides also data for financial literacy (see OECD 2018 and OECD 2023).

In Table 3.4.1, an overview of the source instruments and original variable names of the constructs of interest is presented across PISA. Note that, the HISCED variable is not reported in the 2000 dataset. The construct 'immigration status' was reported in the students' questionnaires in earlier cycles and in the home questionnaires in later cycles. Also, the 'immigration status' is derived from the question of country of birth, i.e., a question which has three parts: the first is the of birth of the student (country) which is self-reported: the second and third parts refer to the parents' country of birth (where 1=Country of test and 2=other). Table 3.4.2 describes the spreadsheet indicators that were derived from the PISA data, as well as details on their availability across PISA cycles.

Table 3.4.1 Source instruments and variable names in PISA

Construct	Source instruments	Variable names in source data							
		2000	2003	2006	2009	2012	2015	2018	2022
Gender	Student questionnaire	ST03Q01	ST03Q01	ST04Q01	ST04Q01	ST04Q01	ST004D01T	ST004D01T	ST004D01T
Socio-economic	Student questionnaire		HISCED	HISCED	HISCED	hisced	HISCED	HISCED	HISCED
Immigration status	Student questionnaire	ST16Q01	ST15Q01	ST11Q01	ST17Q01	ST20Q01	ST019AQ01T	ST019AQ01T	ST019AQ01T

Table 3.4.2 Indicator codebook for PISA- based spreadsheet indicators

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisam_i1	Mean mathematics test score	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i1_2a	Mean mathematics test score by gender: girls	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i1_2b	Mean mathematics test score by gender: boys	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i1_3a	Mean mathematics test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisam_i1_3b	Mean mathematics test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i1_4a	Mean mathematics test score by immigration status: students not born in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i1_4b	Mean mathematics test score by immigration status: students born in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i2_2a	Average mathematics test score achieved by girls in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i2_2b	Average mathematics test score achieved by boys in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i2_3a	Average mathematics test score achieved by high SES students in % of total population average in country	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i2_3b	Average mathematics test score achieved by lower SES students in % of total population average in country	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i2_4a	Average mathematics test score achieved by migrant students in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i2_4b	Average mathematics test score achieved by non-migrant students in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i3	Percent (%) of absolute low performers in mathematics	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisam_i5	Ratio of mathematics test scores by students with higher educated parents vs no higher educated parents	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i6	Ratio of boys/girls mathematics test scores	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i7	Ratio of migrant/non-migrant mathematics test scores	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i9	Relative mathematics test scores by parental SES & gender	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i9_f_0	Relative mathematics test scores by parental SES & gender: girls with no parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i9_f_1	Relative mathematics test scores by parental SES & gender: girls with at least one parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i9_m_0	Relative mathematics test scores by parental SES & gender: boys with no parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisam_i9_m_1	Relative mathematics test scores by parental SES & gender: boys with at least one parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i1	Mean science test score	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i1_2a	Mean science test score by gender: girls	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisasc_i1_2b	Mean science test score by gender: boys	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i1_3a	Mean science test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i1_3b	Mean science test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i1_4a	Mean science test score by immigration status: student was not born in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i1_4b	Mean science test score by immigration status: student was born in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i2_2a	Average science test score achieved by girls in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i2_2b	Average science test score achieved by boys in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i2_3a	Average science test score achieved by high SES students in % of total population average in country	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i2_3b	Average science test score achieved by lower SES students in % of total population average in country	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i2_4a	Average science test score achieved by migrant students in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisasc_i2_4b	Average science test score achieved by non-migrant students in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i3	Percent (%) of absolute low performers in science	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i5	Ratio of science test scores by students with higher educated parents vs no higher educated parents	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i6	Ratio of boys/girls science test scores	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i7	Ratio of migrant/non-migrant science test scores	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i9	Relative science test scores by parental SES & gender	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i9_f_0	Relative science test scores by parental SES & gender: girls with no parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i9_f_1	Relative science test scores by parental SES & gender: girls with at least one parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i9_m_0	Relative science test scores by parental SES & gender: boys with no parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisasc_i9_m_1	Relative science test scores by parental SES & gender: boys with at least one parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisar_i1	Mean reading test score	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i1_2a	Mean reading test score by gender: girls	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i1_2b	Mean reading test score by gender: boys	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i1_3a	Mean reading test score by SES: at least one parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i1_3b	Mean reading test score by SES: no parent has a higher education degree	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i1_4a	Mean reading test score by immigration status: student was not born in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i1_4b	Mean reading test score by immigration status: student was born in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i2_2a	Average reading test score achieved by girls in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i2_2b	Average reading test score achieved by boys in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i2_3a	Average reading test score achieved by high SES students in % of total population average in country	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisar_i2_3b	Average reading test score achieved by lower SES students in % of total population average in country	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i2_4a	Average reading test score achieved by migrant students in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i2_4b	Average reading test score achieved by non-migrant students in % of total population average in country	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i3	Percent (%) of absolute low performers in reading	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i5	Ratio of reading test scores by students with higher educated parents vs no higher educated parents	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i6	Ratio of boys/girls reading test scores	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i7	Ratio of migrant/non-migrant reading test scores	2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i9	Relative reading test scores by parental SES & gender	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i9_f_0	Relative reading test scores by parental SES & gender: girls with no parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i9_f_1	Relative reading test scores by parental SES & gender: girls with at least one parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

Indicator	Indicator description	Time coverage
pisar_i9_m_0	Relative reading test scores by parental SES & gender: boys with no parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022
pisar_i9_m_1	Relative reading test scores by parental SES & gender: boys with at least one parent with higher education	2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, 2022

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Project Name: Strategies for Achieving Equity and Inclusion in Education, Training and Learning in Democratic Europe (STRIDE)

Coordinator: OsloMet – Oslo Metropolitan University, Oslo, Norway - lhuang@oslomet.no

Consortium:

- Oslo Metropolitan University, NOVA, Oslo, Norway
- Jagiellonian University (JU), Poland
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA), Greece
- VIA University College, Denmark
- TÁRKI Social Research Institute (TÁRKI), Hungary
- Roehampton University (RU), United Kingdom
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Partners	Contact Person	Contact email
P1 - Oslo Metropolitan University	Lihong Huang	lhuang@oslomet.no
P2 - National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	Dimitris Parsanoglou	dimparsa@soc.uoa.gr
P3 - VIA University College	Lillian Buus	libu@via.dk
P4 - Lifelong Learning Platform	Veronica Arduino	projects@lllplatform.eu
P5 - TÁRKI Social Research Institute	István György Tóth	toth@tarki.hu
P6 - Jagiellonian University	Magdalena Ślusarczyk	magdalena.slusarczyk@uj.edu.pl
P7 - Roehampton University	Bryony Hoskins	bryony.hoskins@roehampton.ac.uk

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